

Lesson Observation form

Lesson # Title:	
Version:	<input type="checkbox"/> Blackboard <input type="checkbox"/> Projector

Date:	
School:	
School type:	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Private <input type="checkbox"/> Government-aided 2. <input type="checkbox"/> Low performing school <input type="checkbox"/> High performing school
Observer(s):	

Scheduled start/end time of lesson	
Number of students attending	
Number of teachers in class	
Type of technology teacher uses	<input type="checkbox"/> laptop <input type="checkbox"/> smart phone <input type="checkbox"/> pad <input type="checkbox"/> projector

See Instruction page: '**Instructions before the observation starts**' and '**Observation materials**'

Pre-lesson

<p>Record what the teacher has done before the lesson, including:</p> <p>For the blackboard version: Note if anything is written on the blackboard.</p> <p>For the projector version: Note whether the projector is set up and ready for use, has the lesson set up and is ready for use</p>	
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Equipment/technology used during lesson

<p>Note the type of equipment/technology used.</p> <p>For the blackboard and projector version: Note if the students have response cards.</p> <p>For the projector version: Note whether the projector is set up and ready for use, has the lesson set up and is ready for use. Note the type of audio-visual equipment used: (smart phone/projector).</p> <p>Note if there are any power outages or loss of Internet connection during the lesson and how these are managed.</p>	
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Start of the lesson/timing

Planned start time of the lesson:		
Actual start time of lesson: [Do not let teacher or students know you are timing lesson.]		
If there is a substantial gap between the planned start time and when the lesson started, note what happened during that time.		
Keep track of whether more or less time is used for the review of the previous lesson, the activity, and the wrap-up.	Review	Actual time spent:
	Activity	Actual time spent:
	Wrap up	Actual time spent:

See observer instructions: "During the lesson"

Review of previous lesson

Start time of the review:	
Did all the students respond to review questions? Did the teacher explain the answers?	
Did the teacher review the key messages from the previous lesson and check to see if there were any questions or misunderstandings?	

Lesson activity

Start time of the lesson activity:	
<p>Did all the students participate (small groups, individual)?</p> <p>Were the activities clear after teacher explanations?</p> <p>Did you observe any adverse outcomes, or were there observations that might indicate an adverse outcome?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• A student or teacher misunderstanding an explanation or example• Conflict between students, students and teachers, or others• Distraction due to irrelevant, excessive, or difficult questions from students• Any other adverse outcome <p>Did you observe any transfer of learning, or were there observations that might indicate transfer of learning?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Transfer of learning to other fields, besides health• Transfer of learning to practical choices about what to believe or do, in daily life• Any other transfer of learning	

Wrap up

Start time Wrap up	
Did all the students respond to wrap up question(s)? Did the teacher explain the answers?	
Did the teacher repeat the key messages and ask the students to make sure they have them in their notes?	
Did she give the assignment and information about the next lesson?	
Did she check whether the students had questions or misunderstandings?	
Other	
End time Wrap up	

Post lesson

Overall, teachers: how did the teacher appear to respond to the lesson? (Did they seem to enjoy it? Did the teacher get frustrated or bored? Did they say anything about the lesson?)	
Overall, students: how did the students appear to respond to the lesson? (Did they seem to enjoy it? Did they seem engaged? Did they get frustrated or bored? Did you hear them saying anything about the lesson to each other?)	
Overall, School environment: how did the school environment appear to facilitate the lesson delivery?	
Did you observe any adverse outcomes, or were there observations that might indicate an adverse outcome?	
Did you observe any transfer of learning, or were there observations that might indicate transfer of learning?	

Summarize the main findings here

Instructions for observers

Instructions before the observation starts:

- Review the lesson before the lesson and bring a copy with you to follow along while observing the lesson.
- Share the study objectives. (Remind them that we are observing how the students and teachers interact with the materials)
- Explain the data collection methods we are using for the observation (non-participatory observation).
- Sit in the back of the class to ensure that there is no class distraction

Observation materials:

- Observation Guide (printed)
- Notebooks
- Pens/pencils
- Identification card (mandatory- if visiting study participant for the first time)
- Covid-19 PPE (masks, sanitizer etc)
- Voice recorder/camera

During the lesson

Follow along in the lesson plan, so you can note how the teacher uses and understands it, e.g., whether the teacher misunderstands or skips steps. Note things like:

- What seems to work well, or not well from the teacher's side
- What the students and teacher seem to like or dislike
- What the students and teacher seem to misunderstand
- Anything else that you think is important for the effective use of the resources